

Cone Beam Computed Tomography in Endodontics (Part II)

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Applications of CBCT in Endodontics

CBCT and Tooth Morphology

An accurate portrayal of root canal anatomy is a prerequisite for successful diagnosis and treatment. Every tooth is anatomically unique. The internal anatomy of a tooth poses a challenge in successfully diagnosing, localising, negotiating, disinfecting and filling the root canal system. Anatomical complexities can compromise treatment outcome. Owing to the two-dimensional nature of conventional radiology, it cannot reveal the actual number of canals present in teeth. Studies have highlighted that CBCT is superior to conventional radiography in revealing the number of roots.

The clinician should be aware of the dental anomalies and the anatomic variations in every tooth to ensure endodontic success. One common method of evaluating root morphology is periapical radiography. This is a cost-efficient and simple to use technique; however, superimposition and image distortion can be some potential disadvantages.

Descriptive studies have shown that CBCT can accurately highlight root morphology and overcome the flaws in conventional radiography.

Number and Shape of The Root Canals

Some authors believe that conventional radiographs fail to identify the number of canals present in teeth subsequently compromising the outcome. Pre-operative knowledge of the canal anatomy can lead to a conservative cavity preparation and avoidance of mishaps such as ledge formation, canal transportation and perforation.

Localisation of Canals

Pre-operative knowledge of the tooth anatomy can pre-empt endodontic complexities and improve treatment outcome. Anatomic challenges may hinder endodontic success. Maxillary first molar usually has three roots and four canals. An in vivo study was done where maxillary first and second molars were sectioned and the number of canals was determined only to find that there was 80% correlation between CBCT and sectioning. The

disadvantage was a small sample size.

Studies have reported the presence of a fourth canal in 67.14% of the teeth. It has been concluded that the reliability of CBCT imaging to detect the additional canals in the maxillary molar increased with magnification.

Calcified Canals

According to Ball, intra-operative CBCT can be useful for the assessment of the depth of the calcification to guide the clinician for locating and assessing the patent part of the canals. In addition, when a complete calcification is detected, CBCT can be used to study the apical pathosis to avoid perforation of a completely calcified canal. It can be used in cases with complex tooth anatomy within the realms of dose considerations.

CBCT and Canal Curvature

Estrela et al assessed the curvature of the root canals with the aid of CBCT. CBCT is a reliable method to assess the radius of curvature which can reduce the aberrations and chances of instrument fracture.

Complex Root Anatomy

Dens invaginatus is a malformation caused due to the infolding of the enamel organ into the dental papilla during the stages of tooth development. CBCT can be useful in assessment of teeth with complex tooth anatomy. There is a shortage of studies which describe the endodontic treatment of dens invaginatus. Studies by some authors justify the use of cone beam computed tomography for teeth with complex aberrations (such as dens invaginatus) in cases where periapical radiography does not reveal the information required for the management and treatment of such teeth.

Concluding Remarks

Conventional radiographs can assist the clinician to build a mental image of the tooth. Accuracy is however dependent on factors such as the clinician's skill, knowledge, experience and the quality of the radiographs. CBCT is a useful tool in the interpretation of the anatomy of the tooth morphology where parallax technique and microscopes have failed to reveal the true picture. The root morphology can be well visualised and the canals can be

mapped. A limited field of view with a high-resolution CBCT scanner can be used when periapical radiography is not able to provide the necessary information on the root canal anatomy. It is imperative to ensure that the radiation levels are justified and optimised. There is still scope for further evidence that will highlight the accuracy of CBCT for root canal morphology.

CBCT and Apical Periodontitis

Introduction

Apical periodontitis is defined as a dynamic encounter between the microbes and host defence system at the interface between the infected radicular pulp and periodontal ligament. This results in inflammation, periapical destruction and resorption, eventually manifesting as various histopathological forms of periapical lesions.

The aim of endodontic treatment is to preserve the tooth in function and to promote periapical healing. Currently, the method of choice to view periapical changes is radiography (digital or conventional). Unfortunately, periapical radiography may not be able to reflect the changes in the cancellous bone. In the initial stages of apical periodontitis, the periapical changes are minimal and working towards a diagnosis is a challenging task. This can be a cause for operator confusion and patient frustration in the diagnosis of the causative tooth. CBCT is highly sensitive in recognition of apical periodontitis. It can detect endodontic lesions before they become apparent on conventional radiographs. Early diagnosis of apical periodontitis can improve endodontic outcome.

Detection of Apical Periodontitis

It is well established from the results of *ex vivo* studies with reference standards, that is where the periapical status is known before hand, that CBCT is more accurate than periapical radiography to detect periapical periodontitis. In one of the first studies to compare the prevalence of periapical lesions using CBCT and conventional radiographs. They assessed periapical lesions on⁴⁶ maxillary and mandibular posterior teeth using parallax periapical radiography and CBCT. Periapical radiographs could diagnose lesions in thirty-two teeth. On the other hand, CBCT could detect lesions on an additional 10 (31%). Assessment of the periapical status of individual roots revealed that CBCT could detect 62% more lesions than conventional radiographs. This could be attributed to minimisation of geometric distortion and anatomical noise in the maxillary and mandibular second molar region.

It is well documented that CBCT is more accurate in determination of periapical lesions than conventional radiographs. Cone beam computed tomography may reveal the presence of previously undiagnosed pathoses. The increased accuracy of CBCT images in identifying periapical radiolucencies should result in a more objective and accurate assessment of the outcome of pulp preservation, primary root canal and secondary root canal treatment as well as periapical micro-surgery.

Concluding Remarks

- The sensitivity of CBCT is higher than periapical radiography.
- Due to the limitations of conventional radiography, the size of periapical lesions is underestimated when compared to CBCT;
- Current evidence suggests that CBCT has a higher sensitivity than periapical radiography for the detection of periapical lesions;
- Cone beam computed tomography may be indicated to aid the diagnosis of (non-)odontogenic pain when clinical examination and conventional radiographic assessment are not clear;
- Cone beam computed tomography may be considered when (in) direct pulp capping or pulpotomy is being planned in extensively carious teeth where periapical radiography does not reveal anything untoward.
- In cases of poorly localised symptoms when clinical and periapical radiography does not reveal any evidence of pathology, CBCT can be a saviour.

The detection of apical periodontitis by CBCT can influence endodontic diagnosis, instrumentation, disinfection and prognosis. CBCT should be reserved for diagnosing periapical pathology in symptomatic patients where clinical and radiographic imaging is unremarkable.

CBCT and Endodontic Outcome

Introduction

‘Outcome is defined as the measurement of success of a treatment in a designated time frame’. In endodontics, outcome can be determined by evaluation of clinical symptoms and radiographic interpretation. Assessment of outcome is considered imperative as chronic apical periodontitis can exist even in the absence of clinical signs and symptoms. Needless to state, any outcome can directly influence a treatment plan. To give an example, success of primary root canals is perceived to be in the range of 60–100% in traditional cases demonstrating healing outcomes, but when outcome assessment is done using CBCT a lower healing rate is noted. Why is this so? Because CBCT can accentuate lesions which are otherwise not visible.

Various studies have compared the outcome of root canal treatment by CBCT and conventional periapical radiography to come to the conclusion that CBCT can discover 20–35% more lesions. Other major findings to name a few are CBCT can detect bone destruction before it becomes evident on conventional radiographs. CBCT can detect signs of disease (such as periapical radiolucency and widened periodontal ligament space) even though conventional radiograph displayed healing.

Outcome of treatment is improved if clinical signs are treated before the development of the disease. Outcome assessment is important before placing a coronal restoration. CBCT is not routinely used for assessment of apical periodontitis, due to raised exposure parameters but it can be used in cases where pain and

clinical signs of periapical inflammation do not correlate with periapical radiographs. Additionally, CBCT can be used for the volumetric measurement of periapical healing where measurement of the volume of a periapical lesion could give an insight towards periapical healing.

Histopathological examination is another method to confirm the presence of apical lesions. Some studies have concluded that radiographs can be used to assess the presence/absence of apical periodontitis but they are not a reliable indicator of the true histological picture.

CBCT demonstrated increased sensitivity and accuracy in the diagnosis of apical periodontitis in contrast to periapical radiography.

Researchers used CBCT and conventional radiography to compare the quality of root canal treatment. CBCT revealed a higher number of endodontic failures as compared to conventional radiography.

Concluding Remarks

There is a demonstrable need to have an accurate, quantitative and robust system to evaluate the outcome of endodontic treatment. Such a system provides innumerable benefits like accurate

outcome assessment and measurement of healing. It can be concluded from the evidence mentioned in the paragraphs above that due to the limitations of conventional radiography, the size of the periapical radiolucency can be underestimated. On the other hand, CBCT has higher sensitivity as compared to conventional radiography in the detection of periapical pathology. Specificity, however, is similar for both the systems.

CBCT may play a pivotal role in endodontic research it can be used to evaluate the outcome in various treatment strategies such as preparation and instrumentation techniques. On the contrary, there is absence of concrete evidence justifying the use of CBCT in post endodontic treatment owing to increase radiation. Need of the hour is further evidence in the assessment of endodontic outcome.

To be continued.....
(It's a review of literature and not an original article)

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